

CASE REPORT

Recurrent Calcifying Fibrous Tumour in Axilla: A Rare Case Report

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INTRODUCTION

Calcifying fibrous tumour is a rare benign lesion. Calcifying fibrous tumor (CFT), synonymous with a calcifying fibrous pseudotumor, is a rare, distinct tumor-like soft tissue lesion that usually affects children and young adults, with in their subcutaneous and deep of tissues of extremities, trunk, neck and scrotum^{1,2}.

Calcifying fibrous tumor (CFT), originally defined by Rosenthal and Abdul-Karim (1) as a childhood fibrous tumor with psammoma bodies, was subsequently renamed by Fetsch et al(2) as a calcifying fibrous pseudo tumor. It has tendency of non destructive local recurrence. Histologically, it is characterised by a non-encapsulated, well-circumscribed mass, containing dense hyalinised collagen, bland spindle cells, lymphoplasmacytic infiltrate and psammoma bodies, or diastrophic calcifications.(3)

CASE REPORT

A 7 year-old child presented with slow growing swelling over left axilla. Patient was operated for similar swelling 4 years back. Clinical examination revealed a firm, well defined mobile non tender swelling of size 8x5 cm in left axilla. The patient's complete blood count and other routine bio-chemical values were within normal limits. There was no family history. MRI scan revealed multiple altered signal intensity masses in left axillary region, few of them are conglomerated to each other with internal hypo intensities. Excisional biopsy was performed and sent for histopathological examination.

Grossly three grey white to grey brown well circumscribed, lobulated firm soft tissue masses of size 8x8x3.5, second 6.5x4.5x3.5 and smallest was of 2x1.5x1cm were present. External surface of all masses was capsulated globular grey white. Cut surface of all was fibrous grey white.

Microscopically sections show presence of loose

hyalinized bands of collagen, hypocellular in nature, along with areas of dystrophic calcification, presence of lymphoid follicles with germinal centres and large number of reactive plasma cells favouring calcifying fibrous pseudotumour.

DISCUSSION

Calcifying fibrous tumor (CFT) is a rarely seen entity that usually occurs in children and young adults, with a slight increase in risk in women. Clinically, it appears as a slow growing, non tender mass.

These lesions were originally described as arising in the sub cutaneous and deep soft tissues, mostly in the extremities and the neck areas² but more recently CFT have been found to be ubiquitous.

Most lesions are solitary but multi focal lesions are also reported specially arising from pleura and peritoneum and uncommonly in mesentery^{4,5}. Malignant transformation has not been reported⁶.

A few were thought to evolve from inflammatory myofibroblastic tumor(IMT), but larger studies failed to confirm this and ultra structural studies revealed fibroblastic features^{4,7}. However, in the literature, there are cases that maybe related to trauma and Castleman's disease⁸⁻¹².

Nascimen to et al have observed local recurrences in 3 of 10 patients in his study¹³. Ultra structural studies show that calcifications occur as a result of cytoplasmic degeneration in the fibroblasts^{10,13}. The local recurrence rate for CFT has been estimated to be approximately 10%. the rate of recurrence in gastrointestinal CFTs as opposed to CFTs arising at other sites remains unclear. Some authors have suggested that gastric CFTs, for example, have no tendency for local recurrence compared to soft tissue CFTs¹⁴.

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The histopathological features of CFTs are generally easily recognizable from other reactive or benign neoplastic lesions. Inflammatory myofibroblastic tumor (IMT), Plexiform fibromyxoma, reactive nodular fibrous pseudo tumor (RNFP), nodular fasciitis, desmoid fibromatosis, giant cell fibroma, desmoplastic fibroblastoma, fibroma of tendon sheath and calcifying aponeurotic fibroma might be considered in the differential diagnosis. Amyloid fibromas show positive staining with Congo red¹⁵.

There are few studies regarding cytogenetic abnormalities in calcifying fibrous tumors. By using fluorescent in situ hybridization, Hoffmann et al attempted to detect trisomy 7 and trisomy 8 which has been reported in other benign fibrous tumors. Due to the low signal intensity, they were not able to complete the study¹⁶.

In another study, Fukunaga et al found that CFT had a diploid DNA content by flow cytometry¹⁷. Whether CFT is a true neoplasm or an active process still remains unknown¹⁶⁻¹⁸. Future molecular studies can be helpful for detecting the biologic behavior of CFT.

Further studies are needed to clarify the recurrence rate of CFTs in different anatomic sites. Such studies could drive guidelines for management of patients with CFT. In summary, CFT is a rare soft tissue neoplasm and conservative excision is sufficient to cure the patient. However, local recurrence can be seen in some cases. Thus clinical follow up is important. These lesions may be identified more often in the future due to increased awareness and technical advances in diagnosis.

Fig 1: Gross Specimen

Fig 2: 4x

Fig 3: 40x

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